

NON-ISOTHERMAL CRYSTALLIZATION BEHAVIORS OF HDPE/MWCNT NANOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have attracted a great deal of interests during the past two decades as a promising filler in polymer-based nanocomposites because of their special properties.¹⁻⁵ Owing to the exceptional intrinsic properties of the filler particles, novel materials have been envisaged, which could exhibit unprecedented property enhancements, in particular, at filler loadings much lower than in conventional composite technology. In the field of thermoplastic nanocomposites, the reported property enhancements include improved mechanical performance, high thermal and electrical conductivity, increased crystallization rate, and altered rheological behavior.^{4,5} The successful development of promising MWCNTs/polymer nanocomposites to a large extent depends on the ability to disperse the MWCNTs homogeneously in the polymer matrices and to ensure strong MWCNT-polymer interfacial adhesion for good stress transfer.

The homogeneous dispersion of carbon nanotubes is not easy to achieve, especially in nonpolar polymer matrices such as polyolefin because carbon nanotubes tend to form aggregates that are thermodynamically stabilized by van der Waals forces and numerous π - π interactions between the tubes. Various methods have been used to disperse these aggregates such as ultra-sonification, use of surfactant, chemical functionalization of the nanotube surface and *in situ* polymerization. *In situ* polymerization is a promising approach for the preparation of polyolefin nanocomposites without deteriorating the intrinsic properties of MWCNTs. Recently, *in situ* polymerization has been performed by many researchers for the fabrication of polyolefin nanocomposites containing carbon nanotubes using not only a supported Ziegler-Natta catalyst, but also

a supported metallocene catalyst.⁸⁻¹⁰ Because the catalyst was physicochemically grafted to the carbon nanotube surface, individual carbon nanotubes were homogeneously coated by polymer chains that grow on the surfaces, preventing carbon nanotubes from aggregating. The product can be used directly or as a master batch for future nanocomposites.¹⁰

Polyethylenes are the most widely used polyolefin-based thermoplastics. In light of the large spectrum of their applications, improvements and technical breakthroughs in these materials can yield significant economic impact. In our previous study, we reported the preparation of nanocomposites of multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) and high-density polyethylene (HDPE) by *in situ* metallocene polymerization and their electrical conductivity and rheological response. As a part of our continuous efforts to investigate the physical properties of the nanocomposites, the present work provides a direct comparison between the achieved performance levels after incorporation of nanotubes on additional fronts, i.e., thermal behavior and crystalline morphology. Because the addition of fillers significantly affects the crystallization behavior and resulting crystalline morphology of the matrix, this highly oriented columnar morphology of the composites, extending over the entire fiber-matrix interface, is expected to be considerably different from the spherulitic crystal growth commonly encountered in HDPE.⁶

For the crystallization kinetics, isothermal crystallization is normally analyzed using Avrami's equation. In an isothermal crystallization experiment, however, it is difficult to maintain the melted sample in an amorphous state while cooling it to the crystallization temperature. Moreover the crystallization processes encountered in nature tend to be non-isothermal. Non-isothermal crystallization

kinetics has been theoretically explored by Ozawa,⁹ who extended the mathematical derivation proposed first by Evans.⁹ However, Ozawa's theory has some limits. Because this approach compares the degrees of conversion at a fixed temperature for various cooling rates, it can lead to deviations from the predicted linear behavior. We recently devised an analysis scheme to avoid the problem of the Ozawa analysis.⁹ The non-isothermal crystallization kinetics can provide supplementary information about the crystal structure when analyzing crystallization. It may give additional insight into the crystallite structures produced during nanocomposite formation. As a part of our continuous efforts to investigate the physical properties of the nanocomposites, the present work provides a direct comparison between the achieved performance levels after incorporation of nanotubes on additional fronts, i.e., thermal behavior and crystalline morphology.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials:

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) were supplied by Iljin Nanotech Co.(Korea). MWCNT rather than single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNT) were used due to the formation of less dense bundles of entangled nanotubes allowing more catalyst (methylaluminoxane) to reach the inside of the bundles in the solvent than SWNTs. The tube diameter is in the range of 10~15nm and length is in the range of 10~20 μ m. Ethylene (Dong-A Co., 99.9%) was used as a polymerization monomer and dichloro[*rac*-ethylene-bis(indenyl)]Zirconium(IV) (Rac-Et(Ind)₂ZrCl₂) was used as a catalyst. Methylaluminoxane (MAO, 10wt% solution in toluene), a commonly used co-catalyst in metallocene-based olefin polymerization, was also used. All manipulations of the compounds were carried out using a vacuum line, standard Schlenk or cannula techniques under dry argon, and a glove box. After we determined the saturated concentration of MAO supported on the surface of the MWCNTs, we fixed the catalyst on the surface of the MWCNTs. The polymerization reactions were performed in a 5-L high-pressure reactor equipped with a magnetic stirrer. Dried MWCNTs were charged first into the reactor and added to purified toluene. The MWCNT

dispersion was done by a sonic treatment for 90 min at room temperature. After the sonic treatment, a TIBA solution was added to the reactor as a scavenger and then MAO was injected into the slurry. The catalyst fixation was done for 1 h at 40°C. Then, Rac-Et(Ind)₂ZrCl₂ was introduced into the reactor. The activation reaction of the MWCNTs was performed for 1h at 50°C. Injecting ethylene started the polymerization. The polymerization reaction was carried out under a constant pressure of 4 bars of ethylene at 50°C. After a predetermined reaction time, the polymerization was quenched with a diluted HCl solution in methanol. The polymer was precipitated in methanol, filtered, and dried in a vacuum oven.⁶

2.2 Characterization:

Thermal properties of the nanocomposite samples were analyzed using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), performed on a Mettler DSC 30. Prior to analysis, the samples were dried at 80°C in a vacuum oven for 24 hours. Approximately 45mg of the dried composites was used in each run. heated from 25°C to 200°C at a heating rate of 10°C/min, and then cooled at different cooling rates.

2.3 Description of the Theoretical Model :

Here, we briefly present the basic equations from our earlier report.^{7,8} In the Ozawa equation, the Avrami equation is expressed using a cooling rate, as expressed in the following equation:

$$\ln[-\ln(1-x_v(T)_U)] = \ln K(T) - n \ln U \quad (1)$$

where $x_v(T)$ is the volume fraction of the polymer transformed at a temperature T and the cooling rate U , and $K(T)$ is the so-called cooling function, which only varies as a function of the temperature. Because the Ozawa equation is based on the volume fraction of the crystallites, conversion of the weight fraction of the polymer, $x_w(T)$, to the volume fraction of the polymer, $x_v(T)$, is needed. This can be easily done by using the density of the amorphous phase and the density of the crystallized phase.^{7,8} As suggested by the theory, a linear dependence between $\ln K(T)$ and the temperature T is assumed, such that $\ln K(T) = aT + b$. When the temperature reaches the peak of the exothermal curve, T_{\max} , for a given cooling rate, the first and the second derivatives of the curve with respect to the temperature should be zero. Using

equation (1) with this condition, a linear relation between T_{\max} and $\ln(U)$ can be obtained, i.e., $n \ln(U) = aT_{\max} + b - \ln[-\ln(1-x_v(T_{\max})U)]$. Therefore, Eq.(1) can be rewritten as the following:

$$\ln[-\ln(1-x_v(T)U)] = a(T - T_{\max}) + \ln[-\ln(1-x_v(T_{\max})U)] \quad (2)$$

Hence the value of the parameter a can be estimated from the slope of a plot of $\ln[-\ln(1-x_v(T)U)]$ against $T - T_{\max}$. In addition, plotting T_{\max} versus $\ln(U)$ gives a straight line whose slope is n/a and intercept is $(\ln[-\ln(1-x_v(T_{\max})U)] - b)/a$; thus, all of the parameters can be determined without resorting to any numerical process.^{7,8}

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Thermal Properties and Non-isothermal Crystallization Kinetics.

We successfully prepared polyethylene (PE) / multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) nanocomposites with various weight fractions using *in situ* metallocene polymerization.⁶ Although nanocomposites with a variety of MWCNT concentrations were synthesized, two samples containing 1.5-wt% MWCNT and 2.4-wt% MWCNT were mainly used in this study to see the effect of MWCNT addition on the thermal properties. Carbon nanotubes have high electron affinities due to many π electrons similar to C_{60} ; whereby, it has been proposed to act as a scavenger of free radicals.³⁸ Thermal stabilities (onset temperature, degradation temperature) were dramatically enhanced with the MWCNT-addition. An increase in the degradation temperature as high as 50°C was achieved for PE/MWCNT (12.4) in a N_2 atmosphere. This result implies that good dispersion and enhanced interfacial adhesion between MWCNT could hinder the flux of degradation products and, finally, delay the onset of degradation.

It is known that the thermal degradation of polyethylene occurs by chain scission.¹⁰ At temperatures in excess of approximately 400°C, the C-C bonds of the polyethylene backbone spontaneously break to yield two shorter chains, each of which is furnished with a terminal radical. Once the terminal radicals have been produced they may undergo “backbiting” reactions. Backbiting results in the emission of low molecular weight alkanes and alkenes.⁶ Carbon nanotubes have high electron affinities due to many π electrons similar to C_{60} ; whereby,

it has been proposed to act as a scavenger of free radicals.¹⁰ Thermal stabilities (onset temperature, degradation temperature) were dramatically enhanced with the MWCNT-addition. An increase in the degradation temperature as high as 50°C was achieved for PE/MWCNT (12.4) in a N_2 atmosphere. A similar result regarding the stabilities of PE/CNT nanocomposites was reported by Li et al.:¹⁰ however, this was much higher than the result by Watt et al’s who achieved approximately an 18 °C increase in the degradation temperature of PE in N_2 with ~14wt% MWCNTs.³⁸ The difference is attributable to the different mixing procedure. Watt et al. used a melt blending method while Li et al. used a solution blending method. We used the *in situ* polymerization method. This result implies that good dispersion and enhanced interfacial adhesion between MWCNT could hinder the flux of degradation products and, finally, delay the onset of degradation. The degradation temperature of MWCNTs is known to be approximately 600~700 °C in the air and the thermal conductivity of the MWCNT is known to be above 1500 $Wm^{-1}K^{-1}$. MWCNTs act like inorganic fillers, but, due to the strong adhesion between PE molecules and the nanotube walls, thermal energies were well transferred to the carbon nanotubes to delay the onset of the composite degradation.

DSC scans can be seen in Figure 1. All of the samples exhibit a single crystallization exotherm. The main changes are in the characteristic onset and peak crystallization temperatures, i.e., in the values of the associated enthalpies and the peak broadening effects in the nanocomposites compared to neat HDPE. We can see that the onset temperatures of the nanocomposites are higher than those of neat HDPE, which implies that for all *in situ* polymerized nanocomposite samples, the supercooling necessary for the crystallization was much lower. This result is a direct consequence of the remarkable nucleation effect caused by the MWCNTs. Therefore, the crystallization temperature increases with MWCNT content as a result of the nucleating action of MWCNT.^{6,7,8} The fact that HDPE/MWCNT (2.4 wt%) composites exhibit nearly the same crystallization temperature indicates that 1.5 wt% MWCNT provides sufficient (or more than sufficient) nucleation sites eliminating nucleation as a rate limiting step.⁹

Figure 2 displays a linear variation of the maximum temperature of the crystallization isotherm, T_{\max} , of HDPE and the nanocomposites with the logarithm of the cooling rates ($\ln(U)$). The predicted behavior is observed in all cases provided the cooling rate is low (<7°C/min). Because less time is available for

crystallization at higher cooling rates, T_{max} decreases as the cooling rate increases. T_{max} of the nanocomposites was higher than that of the neat PE at the same cooling rate, indicating a faster crystallization. As the cooling rate increases, a large fraction of the relative crystallinity occurs after the most rapidly increasing point in the heat flow curve during which the kinetics change to a slower process. Inclusion of more MWCNTs resulted in an increase in the degree of crystallinity.

FIGURE 1. DSC curves of non-isothermal crystallization at different cooling rates: (a) Homo HDPE, (b) HDPE/MWCNT(1.5 wt%) nanocomposite and (c) HDPE/MWCNT(2.4 wt%) nanocomposite.

Considering the large aspect ratio and surface-to-volume ratio of MWCNTs and that most PE molecules are grown vertically from the surface, the crystallinity of the composites would increase with the concentration of the MWCNT. However, excessive addition of MWCNTs creates a large interface between the PE molecules that surround the MWCNTs and those that are grown vertically from the surface of MWCNTs. The interface region forms an amorphous phase and interferes with crystal growth. Thus, the total crystallinity of the composites decreased when the MWCNT concentration was 12.4 wt%. In Table 1, the melting temperatures of the composites are presented after the second heating. In spite of the increase in the content of MWCNTs, T_m does not show any noticeable changes. This indicates that the presence of MWCNT has no influence on the lamella thickness of the PE chains. Independent of the crystallization process, the melting temperatures are constant, and the overall crystallinity increases with MWCNT content. However, excessive MWCNT content provides more area for an amorphous interface between HDPE molecules surrounding different MWCNTs that results in the reduction in the crystallinity.

The plot of $\ln[-\ln(1-x_c(T_U))] / (T - T_{max})$ versus $(T - T_{max})$, shown in Figure 2 gives a straight line with a slope of n/a . The calculated values of the Avrami exponent, n , for neat PE are between 2.6 and 2.9, with an average value of 2.8. (Table 2). This value is close to the characteristic value for spherulitic development arising from athermal instantaneous nucleation.⁸ These findings suggest that spherulites are developed during non-isothermal crystallization of the HDPE homopolymer. The calculated

average value of the Avrami exponent, n , from Figure 4 is approximately 2.56 for HDPE/MWCNT (1.5 wt%) nanocomposite, 1.99 for HDPE/MWCNT (2.4 wt%) nanocomposite and 1.78 for HDPE/MWCNT (7.3 wt%) close to that of the percolation threshold²⁸) nanocomposite (Table 1). The n values approaching 2 indicate that the encapsulation of MWCNTs by *in situ* polymerization obviously causes heterogeneous nucleation and creates the growth mechanism of the 2-dimensional rod shape.

FIGURE 2. Evolution of T_{max} as a function of $\ln(U)$ (a) homo PE, (b) 1.5 wt% PE/MWCNT nanocomposite and (c) 2.4 wt% PE/MWCNT nanocomposite.

TABLE 1 (left) DSC data for homo PE, PE/MWCNT (2.4 wt%), PE/MWCNT (3.5 wt%), PE/MWCNT (7.3 wt%), PE/MWCNT (8.8 wt%), and PE/MWCNT (12.4 wt%) and Table 2 (right) The half crystallization time $t_{1/2}$ and parameter values of n

Sample	Filler content (wt%)	T_m (°C)	Crystallinity (%)
Homo PE		136.15	64.78
PE/MWCNT(1.5)	1.5	136.07	65.29
PE/MWCNT(2.4)	2.4	136.00	66.2
PE/MWCNT(3.5)	3.5	136.60	68.67
PE/MWCNT(7.3)	7.3	137.22	69.16
PE/MWCNT(8.8)	8.8	136.68	74.12
PE/MWCNT(12.4)	12.4	136.10	71.29

Cooling rate (°C/min)	Homo PE		PE/MWCNT(1.5)		PE/MNT(2.4)		PE/MWCNT(7.3)	
	$t_{1/2}$	n	$t_{1/2}$	n	$t_{1/2}$	n	$t_{1/2}$	n
1	3.87	2.89	4.55	3.35	4.71	2.76	9.47	2.21
3	1.76	2.87	1.9	2.53	1.94	2.11	3.86	1.83
5	1.18	2.76	1.32	2.31	1.73	1.57	2.27	1.71
7	0.87	2.66	1.05	2.05	1.42	1.51	1.83	1.38
avg		2.80		2.56		1.99		1.78

3.2 Morphology of the Nanocomposites.

In the absence of MWCNT, HDPE forms large spherulites (20~50 μ m) with slightly twisted lamellae (Figure 3). In contrast, the crystal structure in HDPE/MWCNT (1.5 wt%) composites consists of much smaller crystallites (1~5 μ m). Because of the excessive nucleation sites in HDPE/MWCNT composites, the

crystallites did not grow as large compared to those in neat HDPE molecules. The HDPE molecules in this study are rooted on the MWCNTs surface, such that they cannot move freely to accommodate the low energy conformation in the crystalline state. Rather the HDPE molecules should overcome the entropic penalty of rooting on the MWCNT surface, which would hinder the free-chain conformation. This concept is explained in Figure 4.¹⁰ At the beginning of the process, faster crystallization proceeds due to the nucleating action of the MWCNT surface. However, after the T_{max} , the PE molecules constrained by rooting on the MWCNT surface for further growth. The interface between each HDPE molecules rooted to different MWCNTs forms amorphous part. Thus, the half crystallization time increased with MWCNT inclusion. Due to the restriction of space and less freedom in the conformation, it takes more time for the HDPE molecules to become ordered.

FIGURE 3 (top row) POM images of homo PE at cooling rate, 3°C/min (a) 118°C (b) 117°C (c) 116°C (d) 115°C (magnification x 400) (bottom row) POM images of PE/MWCNT(1.5 wt%) at a cooling rate of 3°C/min. (a) 118°C (b) 117°C (c) 116°C (d) 115°C (magnification x 400)

FIGURE 4. Schematic Diagrams of Conformational Ordering on the MWCNT surface; (a) Melt state (b) Early stage (c) Later stage.¹⁰

4. Conclusions

The non-isothermal crystallization analysis of HDPE and its nanocomposites with MWCNTs provides some important information about the crystalline structures of these materials. The Avrami exponent of the pristine HDPE was close to 3 indicating that the crystallites had a spherulite structure while that of the nanocomposites was close to 2 depending on the concentration of the MWCNTs, indicating the growth of a 2-dimensional rod shape. The morphology of the pristine HDPE was spherulitic, whereas that of the HDPE in the nanocomposites consisted of rod-like structures. The observed behavior can be attributed to the large number of nuclei present on the surface of the MWCNTs. Anchoring the HDPE molecules on the MWCNT surface renders easy conformational ordering in early stages, but anchoring the roots on the MWCNT surface hinders the ordering of the molecules in later stages. Rooting the HDPE on the

surface restricts movement in the later stages and decelerates the crystallization kinetics of HDPE. Thus, the half crystallization time increased with the MWCNT concentration. This investigation confirms that templating on MWCNTs is quite effective for producing aligned PE morphologies. The presented non-isothermal analysis implicitly provides information about the morphological development history and the molecular ordering in the nanocomposites.

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